

Conservation of Momentum/Energy As Conservation of Information in x-t and Quantum Mechanics

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Conservation of momentum and energy (in elastic collisions) is well-known in classical physics and does not follow from any notions of quantum mechanics, i.e. uncertainties in x-t or from special relativity. These two conservations (energy for elastic collisions, however, do carry over into quantum mechanics and are still present in special relativity.

We have suggested that quantum mechanics for a free particle follow from the degeneracy of the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$, i.e. if x_0, t_0 yield an A, the same A follows from $x_0 + \hbar/p$ and $t_0 + \hbar/E$.

In this note, the point we wish to make is the following. In classical physics, conservation of momentum and energy (elastic collision) is related to an interaction which occurs at some x, t. X and t, however, are background variables, they do not govern the conservation laws, they are only linked to a trajectory. Conservation occurs at any x and t. In other words, x,t are present, but completely decoupled from E,p.

In special relativity, this decoupling exists for a particle of rest mass at rest, e.g. m_0 at $x=0$ at t, but not when the particle is seen from a moving frame (constant -v). In such a case, $m_0 \rightarrow m_0 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ $p=0 \rightarrow mv / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$, $t' = t / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and $x' = vt' / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ such that $(x=0, t) \rightarrow (x'=0, t'=0)$. This indicates that p,E differ from x', t' by the factor m_0 for $c=1$. In other words, p and E and x', t' are strongly correlated and are simply multiples of each other. Thus, a fluctuation: \hbar/p and \hbar/E in x', t' should be related to E and p. To see this relation, however, one may note that E,p depend on v and a fluctuation in x', t' may leave $x'=vt'$ unchanged (i.e. the trajectory), but only shift the x', t' value of the E or p hit in an interaction. Thus, E and p exist, are constants, are conserved, but are linked with fluctuations in $x'=\hbar/p$, $t'=\hbar/E$ from the trajectory values of $x'=vt'$. This implies that there is probability for x' and t' in space for a constant E,p. In particular, there is more information for higher E, p values as seen from $t' = \hbar/E$ and $x' = \hbar/p$ fluctuations or information about t' and x' lengths. When two particles interact, one considers one total E and one total p and so instead of two sets of information, there is one set, for E_{total} and p_{total} . This appears to be directly related to conservation of momentum and energy as we discuss and show quantitatively. Thus, because of the close relation between E,p and x', t' and even the fluctuations \hbar/E , \hbar/p , conservation of E and p is related to information in x', t' (fluctuations not trajectory).

Conservation of E,p

Conservation of momentum (p) and energy (E) are basic ideas of Newtonian mechanics which do not follow from any quantum mechanical ideas or ideas of special relativity, it seems, but rather from action-reaction and Newton's second law. If an interaction occurs, it is associated with an x,t, but this is part of the trajectory of the two or more colliding particles. Other than that, x,t have nothing to do with conservation. P and E stand alone as the key variables of interest in conservation.

Special Relativity and the Relationship between E,p and x,t

We argued in the above section that x,t is independent of p,E in Newtonian mechanics. This also holds in a rest frame for a particle with rest mass, m_0 , at x,t , but not in the moving frame. In the moving frame one has:

$$E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((1a)) \quad p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((1b))$$

$$T' = t / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((1c)) \quad X' = vt / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((1d))$$

One may see that E,p are simply m_0 multiplied by t', x' (for $c=1$). Thus, there is a very strong correlation between x',t' and E,p . Physically, however, one would argue that E,p are constants related to an interaction, while x',t' represent a trajectory. In other words, without seeing the Lorentz transformation properties ((1)), one would retain the Newtonian view that x',t' are background variables marking the location and time of a collision, but having nothing to do with conservation.

We argue in contrast that the similarity of E,p and x',t' through the Lorentz transformations carries over to conservation of E, p and information in x',t' , but not through the usual trajectory $x'=vt'$ which may be obtained without any notion of special relativity.

The point of conservation of E and p (consider one dimension for simplicity) for a two body collision is that given an E_1 and E_2 , i.e. two pieces of information, the key is that it is equivalent to any other two pieces of information E_i, E_j such that $E_1+E_2 = E_i+E_j$. Conservation is usually thought of in terms of no new energy being created or lost, but is also the mapping of many E_i, E_j pairs into the same constant E_1+E_2 , which is an information probability statement.

Now the close association of E,p and x',t' in special relativity allows one to write a Lorentz invariant (dot product):

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((2))$$

In Newtonian mechanics, there would be no reason whatsoever to combine E,p, t,x in this manner. In fact, there one desires $x(t)$ with no E or p present, i.e. it is strictly a trajectory viewpoint.

The key idea related to ((2)) is that even though E,p are constant related to a collision and dependent on a constant v and $x'=vt'$ (a classical trajectory), there is a fluctuation in x',t' solution to ((2)), i.e.

If x_0, t_0 yield an A value, the same A value results from $x_0 + \hbar/p$ and $t_0 + \hbar/E$ ((3))

In other words, there are fluctuations linked to t', x' , but based on E,p because of the close relationship of E,p and t',x' in special relativity. These fluctuations remove information as we have argued in previous notes because:

$$-E (\hbar/E) = \hbar \text{ for any } E \quad \text{and} \quad p (\hbar/p) = \hbar \text{ for any } p \quad ((4))$$

Furthermore, these fluctuations represent x',t' probability regions which may be written in terms of the complex probability:

$$\exp(-iEt') \exp(ipx') \quad ((5))$$

This means that $E1'$ and $E2'$ conserve energy to yield $(E1'+E2')$, but any Ei' and Ej' are equivalent in terms of fluctuation information in t' as long as $Ei'+Ej' = E1'+E2'$.

Thus, the idea of information associated with conservation is also associated with fluctuations of x',t' linked to E and p . Quantitatively, the two ideas, namely conservation and fluctuation are linked because:

$$\text{Integral } dx' \exp(-ip3x')\exp(-ip4x') \exp(ip1x)\exp(ip2x) = 0 \text{ if } p1+p2 \text{ not} = p3+p4 \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is a result which has been known since the early days of quantum mechanics.

Thus, the close association of x',t' and E,p in special relativity suggests that conservation of E and p manifest itself somehow in x',t' . This, however, cannot be done through notions of the trajectory, $x'=vt'$, which does not contain notions of E,p , only v .

Conclusion

In conclusion, conservation of momentum and energy (elastic collisions) are well-known ideas from Newtonian mechanics which have nothing to do with quantum mechanics or special relativity there. In other words, x,t marks a collision point, but conservation of momentum/energy only affects the variables E and p . X and t are related to a trajectory $x(t)$ in which one need not even know what energy or momentum is. We note, however, that even in this Newtonian picture, conservation is directly linked to an information probability. In particular, for a given $E1+E2$, any Ei, Ej such that $Ei+Ej=E1+E2$ has the same probability.

In special relativity, we argue that matters are different. There is still the notion of a constant E,p for a constant v and a trajectory $x'=vt'$ (for $x'=0$ at $t'=0$) and at this point one might think that Newtonian ideas still hold. The issue is that x,t and $p=0$, mocc Lorentz transform in exactly the same manner allowing one to write a Lorentz invariant or dot product between E,p and t',x' , something one would never do in Newtonian mechanics. In other words, one has: $A = -Et'+px'$. This invariant allows one to define fluctuations in x',t' , namely $\hbar/p, \hbar/E$, which leave A unchanged. This in turn, leads to a probability scheme for x',t' for constant p,E or $\exp(-iEt')\exp(ipx')$. This means that the probability $\exp(ip1x)\exp(ip2x')$ yields $\exp(i(p1+p2)x')$ which is equivalent to a loss of information or conservation of p . In other words, conservation of p and E is linked to information probability and this probability holds quantitatively for the t',x' fluctuations. In other words, any pi, pj will combine in a collision to form the same fluctuation in x' length $\hbar/(pi+pj)$ if $pi+pj=p1+p2$ (one dimension).

Thus, special relativity leads to quantum mechanics in a way that conservation of momentum and energy (from Newtonian mechanics) extend to x', t' fluctuations. The trajectory $x' = vt'$ is still present, but has nothing to do with conservation like in Newtonian mechanics.